

ANALYSIS OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET FOR SEDATIVE DRUGS REGISTERED IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the assortment of sedative drugs registered in the state register of the Republic of Uzbekistan using content analysis. The results of this analysis of the pharmaceutical market for sedative drugs demonstrate the potential and expediency of developing highly effective drugs based on medicinal plants, which provides an opportunity to expand the range of safe and high-quality sedatives produced in our country.

INTRODUCTION. Currently, new types of sedatives developed from medicinal plants are continuously entering the pharmaceutical market. In the rapidly developing 21st century, economic crises, the increasing number of incurable diseases, environmental degradation, and periodic interstate wars are causing mental health problems, particularly severe stress and psychological strain. This, in turn, means that a person's constant nervous, restless, and depressed state significantly impacts their work and mental performance. Consequently, there is a very high interest and demand among people for drugs with a sedative effect [1].

According to the World Health Organization, the annual growth rate of people suffering from mental stress and neurosis worldwide is 10%. The growing demand for sedatives made from medicinal plant raw materials is primarily because they can be taken by

patients without a doctor's prescription, they do not contain high amounts of potent biologically active substances, there is no risk of overdose, and their broad spectrum of action distinguishes them from synthetic sedatives with these advantages [2,3].

As mentioned above, the production of medicines based on medicinal plant raw materials by domestic manufacturers is considered promising. This is because such drugs are easy and convenient for patients to take, have virtually no side effects, are safe for human use, and possess high therapeutic efficacy. Therefore, this sector is of great importance to the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan [4].

It was deemed appropriate to conduct a content analysis of sedative drugs on the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan, specifically those registered in the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Authorized for Use in Medical

Practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" between 2023 and 2025.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY. To study the product range of sedative drugs registered in the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Authorized for Use in Medical Practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" for the period of 2024-2025.

The study was conducted by performing a content analysis of the information provided in issues No. 28 (2024) and No. 29 (2025) of the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Authorized for

Use in Medical Practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [5, 6].

RESULTS. As of the beginning of the period taken for content analysis in 2024, the range of drugs with a sedative effect comprised a total of 62 items. By 2025, it can be observed that the range of sedatives grew to 95 items. The growth dynamics of the range of registered sedative drugs for 2024-2025 are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Indicators of sedative drugs included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan

State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Drugs registered by domestic manufacturers	Drugs registered by CIS manufacturers	Drugs registered by foreign manufacturers
No. 28 (2024)	27	14	21
No. 29 (2025)	51	26	18

As can be seen from Table 1, during the period from 2024 to 2025, the number of sedative drugs produced in CIS countries increased from 14 to 26 items, while the share of drugs registered by foreign manufacturers decreased from 21 to 18. During the same period, the number of sedative drugs produced by domestic manufacturers rose from 27 to 51 items.

During the study, the proportions of sedative preparations developed by

domestic manufacturers in 2024-2025 were presented. According to the results of a content analysis, the leading liquid dosage forms were tinctures, solutions, and liquid extracts, followed by syrups and medicinal plant raw materials (MPRM). Among solid dosage forms, tablets ranked first, followed by capsules (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Proportions of sedative dosage forms produced by domestic manufacturers in 2024-2025

The research also analyzed the assortment of sedative drugs produced by CIS and other foreign countries and registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2024 to 2025.

During this period, manufacturers from CIS countries registered 40 medicinal products, which were presented in the following forms: tablets (16), capsules (3), drops (4), solutions (3), homeopathic tablets (1), and prolonged-action tablets (1). The results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Proportions of sedative drugs produced in CIS countries in 2024-2025.

During the period from 2024 to 2025, 39 medicinal products from foreign manufacturers were registered,

presented in the following forms: capsules (18), tablets (9), syrups (6), solutions (1), drops (3), and suspensions (2). The obtained results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Proportions of Sedative Medicinal Products Developed in Foreign Countries from 2024-2025

DISCUSSION: An analysis of the data presented above reveals that in the "State Register of Medicines, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment Approved for Use in the Medical Practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan," for the years 2024-2025, tinctures hold the leading position among medicinal products developed by domestic manufacturers. This is followed by solid dosage forms such as tablets, liquid dosage forms like liquid extracts, and then capsules, solutions, medicinal plant raw materials, and syrups. However, it is

notable that dry extracts derived from medicinal plant raw materials have not been registered. This, in turn, is further evidence that developing primary products from the medicinal plants widely available in our Republic and creating various types of pharmaceutical products from them are among the most pressing tasks of our time.

CONCLUSION. Based on the information presented above, it can be concluded that the development of a modern, unique, highly effective, and safe tablet dosage form with a sedative effect, derived from local medicinal plants, is advisable.

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